

Knowledge creation in a nascent biotech innovation system: the case of Pécs city region

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Abstract. This paper presents ongoing work on developing an empirical agent-based model (ABM) of knowledge creation in a biotech innovation system located in a less-developed region. Compared to previous models of knowledge creation in the biotech sector, it focuses on the early stage of innovation pathway development including not only the industry agents but also university sector agents at the level of institutes. To underpin the model at the agent- and system-level with empirical data, personal interviews were conducted and patent data as well as publication data are employed through an elaborated initialization and calibration procedure. The model is fully conceptualized and empirically initialized and is being calibrated for later policy scenario simulations. Thus, the model will provide useful results for regional development policymakers, e.g., by exploring potential effects of Smart Specialization Strategies.

Keywords. Regional knowledge creation, inter-organizational R&D collaboration, agent-based modelling, policy scenarios, biotechnology, publications, patents, Pécs city region

1 Introduction

The important role of regions for creating innovation and thus as a strong driver of regional economic development has for long been recognized and is reflected in the concept of regional innovation systems (see, for instance, Braczyk et al. 1997, Asheim and Isaksen 2002). In the European Union, we have seen remarkable catching-up successes by lagging regions, nevertheless interregional gaps in innovation performance and economic disparities in Europe persist (EC 2017, Meliciani 2016). This has been ascribed to the observation that regional innovation policies have not yet achieved its full effect in disadvantaged regions (see, e.g., Blažek et al. 2014). The EU's Smart Specialization Strategy (S3) specifically aims at strengthening the innovation capacity and competitiveness of regions that are structurally disadvantaged. The S3 concept, going back to Foray et al. (2009), underlines the use of local technological strengths, knowledge resources as well as place-based governance and represents the backbone of the EU's regional innovation policy of the last decade (Guzzo et al. 2018).

The role of S3 in fostering the development of early-stage regional innovation systems in less advanced regions has primarily been associated with creating a regional knowledge base and a dynamic learning process, as well as network integration mechanisms among key innovation actors in industry (Ranga 2018). Hereby, the special role of universities and research organizations as prime sources of knowledge has been highlighted (Vallance et al. 2018, Fotakis et al. 2014).

Our research addresses the issue of early-stage innovation pathway creation in peripheral regions and the pivotal role of universities and research organizations as prime sources of knowledge, focusing on

the region of Pécs in Southern Hungary. Here, an S3 implementation process has been started and biotechnology has been identified as a priority topic. Especially human biotechnology as a business activity is a prior development area in Hungary's R&I strategy, as represented for instance in the Irinyi Plan for Reindustrialisation (MIT 2016, pp. 57-61, Lengyel 2021). On the other hand, it has been argued that political decisions on local or regional priorities would need stronger scientific basis, for instance provided by economic modelling (Varga et al. 2020, Sebestyén and Varga 2019, Balland et al. 2019) and appropriate economic indicators (Szerb et al. 2020). A good example pointing to this direction is the new National Smart Specialization Strategy of Hungary (2021), which explicitly builds on the results of a multi-regional, multi-sectoral economic impact model, i.e., the GMR-Hungary (Varga et al. 2020). According to this document, biotechnology is one of the eight national priority areas for the 2021-2027 period. The region of Pécs (Baranya County) is considered a knowledge region, where strengthening the university-centered innovation ecosystem is a policy objective.

Spatial and technological proximities are core prerequisites for knowledge creation and diffusion both within organizations and regions, and therefore innovation performance (Capello and Varga 2013). By defining a regional knowledge complexity index (KCI¹), Pintar and Scherngell (2021) have recently shown that future regional economic growth is associated with knowledge complexity of the region.

Similarly, within the literature on regional innovation systems (Cooke 1998), related variety has been established as a factor for improving competitiveness by utilizing knowledge spillovers, while unrelated variety is assigned a more defensive, resilience-oriented role against external shocks (Castaldi et al. 2015, Frenken et al. 2007, Fritsch and Kublina 2018). While such arguments have been empirically confirmed for advanced regions, the situation is less clear for less-favoured regions. Where distinctive specialization patterns are absent, the role of unrelated variety might also be crucial for finding new trajectories for the regions (Grillitsch et al. 2018, Trippel et al. 2019), but empirical evidence is still scarce.

This group of complexity-related arguments leads us to take a closer look at knowledge creation in less-favoured regions, focusing on the level of organizations: innovating firms and research organizations create new knowledge and interact with each other to exchange knowledge and to engage in mutual learning. Hereby, we adopt the approach of agent-based modelling and simulation to grasp the evolutionary process that emerges from individual decisions of organizations related with knowledge creation.

This paper develops an empirically guided agent-based model (ABM) of new regional knowledge creation and early regional pathway development focusing on the concrete case of biotechnology in the Pécs city region. The model builds on earlier models developed for single regions and specific industries (Dünser and Korber 2017, Paier et al. 2017, Neuländtner et al. 2019). While those models comprise only industry organizations as decision-making agents in the simulation, our model adds science agents,

¹ The knowledge complexity of a region is hereby related to its diversity in terms of available expertise in different technologies, and the uniqueness of these technologies as compared with other regions.

representing by university institutes and research organizations, as active model elements. Thus, a better representation of knowledge creation processes is achieved by comprising both academic and industrial research, as well as mutual knowledge flows. The model will be initialized and calibrated with empirical data on scientific publications and patent applications from the Pécs city region mainly from the period 2000-2020. With our ABM, the emergence of specialization pathways of the biotechnology sector in the Pécs city region can be explored with scenario simulations, reflecting different framework conditions, i.e., regional research and innovation policies, especially the smart specialization strategy (S3).

The structure of the paper is as follows. Chapter 2 introduces the concept and the basic elements of the ABM approach and sketches the state-of-the-art in empirical ABMs and corresponding policy simulations. Chapter 3 describes the basic elements and processes of the new model. Chapter 4 gives a detailed description of the data used and explicates the initialization procedures, both at the system level, and at the agent level. s n outlook on model implementation, the calibration strategy and potential applications.

2 State-of-the-art: agent-based modelling of regional knowledge creation

Agent-based models (ABMs) are a class of computational models for simulating the simultaneous actions and interactions of multiple agents to resemble the appearance of complex phenomena (Kirman 1997). As such, a key notion is that simple behavioral rules at the micro level generate complex behavior at the macro level, ABMs provide a framework to simulate behavior and interactions of heterogeneous agents within a given environment, with the objective to model the complexity of real-world systems (Nikolic et al. 2013). The advantages of agent-based modelling come from its ability to capture heterogeneity, spatial structure and adaptation, which makes it a useful tool to inform decision-makers in complex systems (Hammond 2015, p 164).

New ABM simulation approaches of regional innovation activity, such as the VISIBLE simulation environment (Pyka et al. 2018), have been used to gain an understanding of regional innovation processes from a micro-level perspective. The strengths of these simulation approaches are the new way of conceptualizing knowledge at the actors' level and the fine-grained implementation of knowledge exchange, learning, and innovation processes, and have been successfully applied to the regional policy context. Ponsiglione et al. (2018) have presented an agent-based computational laboratory, CARIS (Complex Adaptive Regional Innovation System), which aims at evaluating the self-sustainability of regional innovation systems and mechanisms able to trigger powerful innovation and economic growth processes. This model has been applied to lagging regions in Southern Italy, which, notwithstanding noticeable policy interventions, have so far been unable to significantly improve their innovation performances.

Sectoral approaches using ABM have been developed in the field of biotechnology, focusing on R&D and knowledge creation in university-industry relationships (Triulzi et al. 2014). These authors have shown that industry collaboration tend to shift universities towards applied research and that universities tend to benefit from financial resources of the companies. Adequate policies are needed to uphold basic

research capabilities of universities, which are essential attractors for effective interaction with biotech companies.

Regional-sectoral approaches were developed for knowledge creation in the Vienna Life Sciences sector (Dünser and Korber 2017) and the Austrian biotechnology and semiconductor industries (Paier et al. 2017, Neuländtner et al. 2019). Using a sophisticated empirical modelling approach, these models are suitable to account for specific issues of policymakers in ex-ante assessment of policy initiatives. For instance, policy scenarios were simulated describing the effect of regional cluster initiatives or the effect of mission-oriented government funding vs. indirect funds on the innovation output of the regions.

3 Model description

Building on this experience, we develop an empirical ABM which describes how the actors of the biotech innovation system individually and jointly create new knowledge, leading to new knowledge paths in the city region. Compared to previous models of knowledge creation in biotech sector (Dünser and Korber 2017, Paier et al. 2017), it focuses on the early stage of innovation pathway development and include explicitly the university sector at the level of institutes as dynamic model elements (decision making agents), regional characteristics, and region-external knowledge sourcing channels.

3.1 Model structure

The model is composed of heterogenous agents, and their activities and relationships. Besides, there are other entities that form the environment of the model. Agents in the model represent regional innovation system actors from the knowledge exploration and exploitation subsystem as well, namely industry firms and university institutes. Agents from both types are active players in the model, as they have individual characteristics, do research activities, and possibly interact with each other. Two kinds of relationships may take place among any types of agents which are associated with knowledge transfer. On one hand, unintentional knowledge flow may occur in the form of knowledge spillovers. On the other hand, if research is conducted in cooperation with some other organization (firm or university institute) knowledge transfer occurs during the research collaboration. Extra-regional firms and research organizations are not represented at the agent level but they form an external pool of knowledge that is accessible to the agents through extra-regional collaborations under certain conditions.

Both types of agents are characterized by empirically based individual attributes such as *knowledge endowment*, and *organizational figures*.

- *Knowledge endowment* represents the knowledge base of the agent. It is composed of the potential knowledge fields the agent is active in and the corresponding expertise levels.
- *Organizational figures* include the age and size of the organization. It influences agent's ability to innovate and the probability of a research to be successful.

Figure 1: Main elements of the regional knowledge creation model

They also possess partly empirically based strategies, that influence their behavior. These theoretical elements are the following:

- *Learning strategy* determines whether the agent follows a *specialization* or a *diversification strategy* while choosing a research target.
- *Collaboration strategy* determines whether the agent conducts research on its own (*internal research*) or it collaborates with someone else (*collaborative research*).
- *The way of learning* determines whether the agent waits for knowledge spillover (*passive*) or makes efforts to actively engage in research (*active*).

Furthermore, agents have a memory that plays a role in the adaptation of their behavior based on their experiences. These technical model features are the following:

- *Success memory* allows for adaptation of the agent's behavior by updating the strategies based on its failed and successful research efforts.
- *Collaboration memory* contains the set of the recent partners of the agent that makes it possible to put them into preferential position during partner search.

3.2 Knowledge space

The model accounts for knowledge creation and exchange processes as a crucial part of regional innovation systems. Each agent has a knowledge endowment which is represented by knowledge fields that the agent is active on, and their respective expertise levels. While universities use mainly scientific knowledge to conduct basic research, firms are primarily engaged in applied research and accordingly they possess technological knowledge. However, firm and university institute agents both may have technological and scientific knowledge elements as well. The knowledge endowment of an agent is defined as a vector whose elements represent the expertise level of the agent in the respective knowledge fields (Neuländtner 2020). The knowledge endowment K_i of agent i is given by the following vector

$$K_i = (\kappa_{i1}, \kappa_{i2}, \dots, \kappa_{ik}, \eta_{i1}, \eta_{i2} \dots \eta_{il})$$

where $i=1,2,\dots,N$, with N being the number of agents, k is the number of technological fields, and l is the number of scientific fields. If an element of the vector is equal to 0, the agent is not active in the corresponding technology field.

Figure 2: Relationship between technological and scientific knowledge spaces

The agents' knowledge endowment is embedded in a so-called knowledge space. The whole knowledge space is composed of two distinct but interlinked parts. The technological knowledge space is defined as a network of technological fields with weighted links indicating the technological proximity between them. The scientific knowledge space is also represented by a network, where nodes are biotechnology-related scientific fields, and the ties represent the similarity of the knowledge among these fields. In the model, knowledge flows between scientific and technological parts of the knowledge space are enabled by an empirically justified concordance table as shown in Figure 2.

3.3 Model processes

Agents are engaged in independent as well as collaborative research activities, where they exchange knowledge mutually and with actors from outside the region. During this research process, the agents may acquire knowledge gains resulting in knowledge and innovation outputs, and which feed back on the initial agent characteristics.

In the first step, the initial values of input variables are defined. There are three types of input factors that influence the agents' activities. *State variables*, namely *knowledge endowment*, *collaboration memory* and *success memory* are automatically updated during each simulation run. *Decision variables* like *learning strategy*, *collaboration strategy* and the *way of learning* can be updated based on the state variables, depending on the model settings. However, *empirical characteristics* (organization type, age, size) are exogenous variables which are unchanged without an intervention during the simulation.

With a certain probability, the agent attempts to obtain new knowledge in the given timestep. First, the agent chooses a knowledge element from the knowledge space as a *research target*. It may be a field in which the agent is already active, and its aim is to enhance its expertise level, or it is a new field that the agent wishes to get known.

Figure 3: Agent-level research processes. Own elaboration based on Neuländtner et al. 2019

The research target is chosen according to the *learning strategy* of the agent as shown in Figure 4. If its strategy is *specialization*, the agent chooses one of its knowledge elements and makes efforts to increase its expertise in this field on their own or via collaborative research. There are two sub-strategies of specialization: *strengthening* or *catching up*.

Figure 4: Subprocess: Set research target

The first one refers to the strategy when the agent selects its strongest knowledge field (i.e., the one with the highest expertise level) as a research target and seeks to further develop its expertise. In contrast, an agent with a *catching up* specialization sub-strategy tries to develop one of its knowledge elements with lower expertise level. This substrategy enables gradual building of a minimum knowledge base for further research and innovation (Dutrénit 2004). If the agent’s strategy is *diversification*, it chooses a new knowledge element as a research target that was not yet part of its knowledge endowment. There are two types of diversification strategies: *related* and *unrelated variety* (Frenken et al. 2007). *Related variety* describes the sub-strategy when the agent chooses one of the closest knowledge elements to its strongest knowledge element that is not yet included in its knowledge endowment. It is a way to broaden its knowledge base with a knowledge element that is relatively easy to integrate. With an *unrelated variety sub-strategy*, the agent chooses a new knowledge element from the knowledge space that is further away from its strongest knowledge element. The threshold from which it is considered to be further is a matter of model settings. This sub-strategy aims to build a portfolio that makes the organization more resistant to external shocks.

The research process aims to achieve this element, which is possible in a *passive way* through *spillover* or in an *active way* through actual *research*. Spillovers are unintended knowledge flows from one agent to another, representing flows of human capital or tacit knowledge, which are implemented in the model as transfers of knowledge among the agents in the region. If the agent opts to wait for the spillover and the target knowledge element is available at some other player in the region, the agent receives it with a certain probability without research efforts. If the agent decides to be *active* and does not wait for spillover, it will carry out research alone or in cooperation with another player, depending on its *collaboration strategy*. If the collaboration strategy of the agent is *internal*, it conducts research on its own (*internal research*) to achieve its target. In this case, new knowledge is created within the organization based on its internal capabilities. In the case of *collaborative strategy*, *collaborative*

research takes place. It provides an opportunity to acquire knowledge and resources that are otherwise not available for the organization. Collaboration is possible not only among the same types of agents but between university institute and industrial firm agents as well, that allows knowledge flows between the scientific and the industrial sector.

Depending on the *outreach of partner search*, the agent tries to find a regional partner or attempts to acquire its research target from the extra-regional pool of knowledge. If it has the intention and ability to tap knowledge outside of the region – the latter being defined by a sufficiently high level of expertise and agent size –, its outreach is *region external*, otherwise *region internal*. In the case of region internal research, *collaboration memory* influences partner choice as partners from successful collaborations are more likely to be selected again. The agent asks in the first few rounds the organizations from its *collaboration memory* if they have the targeted knowledge element. If it finds an appropriate partner during these attempts, the agent chooses from them for collaborative research. If this chosen agent is also interested in the common research, the *knowledge transferred is enabled*. In each timestep, a certain share of agents is open for collaboration. This share is the same for the active side of collaboration, when agents intend to carry out collaborative research and the passive side, when agents that are asked for collaboration are interested. Otherwise, the agent searches for another partner from the region. If it finds a suitable and interested potential partner, the knowledge transfer between is enabled. If it does not find one, it will start *internal research*.

Figure 5: Subprocess: Collaborative research

If the research is successful, i.e., the research target is achieved, a knowledge gain will be generated. The probability of success depends on the characteristics of the agents involved in the research and the

proximity in the knowledge space between the research target and the knowledge base of the agent: The proximity positively influences the probability of success, as the more similar the new knowledge element is to the existing ones, the easier it is to integrate it. A higher number of the knowledge fields in the agent's knowledge endowment is associated with a higher probability of success, as we assume that agents with experience in more fields have more chance to achieve their research target. These two factors provide a balance between specialized and diversified learning strategies. If the collaborative research is not successful, the agent tries to achieve its research target on its own.

From the knowledge gained, different formal outputs can be created depending on the type of the reached knowledge element. In the case of *scientific* knowledge gain, the result may be a *publication* while *technological* knowledge gain may turn to a *patent* application. Since any agent possibly sets scientific or technological knowledge as the research target, both types of agents can produce patents and publications as well. However, the knowledge gained does not always turn into a *formal output*, an *informal output* generates even in this case. It has a positive effect on the agent's knowledge endowment, but it does not materialize in measurable formal outputs.

As a result of the research process, the *state variables and decision variables* are updated, which feeds back on the input side of the model. The knowledge achieved increases the expertise level of a knowledge element or broadens the knowledge base of the agent. Meanwhile, the expertise level of the unused knowledge elements decreases. In the case of successful collaborative research, the *collaboration memory* is updated with the current partner and the oldest one is deleted from the list. The *success memory* records if the research was successful with the current *learning and collaboration strategy*. Based on these results, the strategies may update depending on the model settings. If the current strategy was successful, the agent is more likely to follow it, while if the research had no result, it would rather change strategy.

4 Empirical data

4.1 Description of data

The described model is applied for the case of the city of Pécs and its surroundings. It is a less favored region on the southwestern part of Hungary where, e.g., the university sector is relatively strong, but the related industry is still weakly developed. Regarding biotechnology, the University of Pécs can be highlighted, which has outstanding educational institutions and research activities in the field of health science, therefore human biotechnology could be a breakthrough point (Lengyel 2021). However, only a few firms exist in the region with R&D in biotechnology as principal activity; most of these firms are primarily active in a wider range of science and technology areas. To underpin the model at the agent- and system-level with empirical data, different data sources are tapped. On the one hand, personal interviews were conducted with representatives of 14 biotech related firms and 12 university institutes and research groups in Pécs and its surroundings (Varga-Csajkás 2020). This research aimed to gain information for region-specific model features and processes. On the other hand, for initialization,

calibration and validation we use patent data from PATSTAT database and publication data from the Web of Science.

4.2 Use of data

A crucial point of the agent initialization is the empirical underpinning of the knowledge endowment. In our model, each agent possesses a set of knowledge elements and the corresponding expertise levels that makes up its knowledge endowment. Firm and university agents both may have

- technological and
- scientific knowledge elements as well.

Technological knowledge elements correspond to International Patent Classification (IPC) codes that are assigned to biotechnology patents according to the OECD (2009) classification. It lists more detailed categories, but for simplicity they were aggregated to 3-digit codes, so called subclasses (e.g., C12N). This list was supplemented with the most common IPC codes which occurred during a patent search at the patents.google.com with the KNOWMAK KET Industrial biotechnology subclasses (see Appendix 4) as keywords². For the final list of the 25 biotechnology-related IPC Subclasses see Appendix 1.

To initialize the knowledge endowment of the given agent set, patents from the PATSTAT database were used. The geographical delimitation was done according to the inventor's addresses, so all patents were obtained from the database which has at least one inventor from Baranya. Since the agent is not the person but the organization, we identified the firm or university institute for each inventor. The knowledge element – represented by the patent subclass – became part of the knowledge endowment of the inventor's organization. The expertise level for each technological knowledge element was determined on the basis of the number of the agent's patents in the current patent subclass. Fractional counting was applied according to IPC subclasses and inventors. E.g., if a patent has 2 IPC subclasses and 3 inventors, each inventor provides a 1/6 share to his/her organization's technological knowledge. Due to the low number of publications and inventors (33 publications and 50 inventors from the region) it was possible to identify the firm or university institute of each inventor from the region. It should be noted that identification of the inventor's affiliation was not always straightforward, so how special cases are treated is described in the Appendix 2.

Scientific knowledge elements are based on publication data obtained from the Web of Science. They are operationalized by biotechnology-related WoS Research Areas (RAs). To define the biotechnology-related RAs, we searched for the publications which has the string "biotec*" in the name of the RA³ from 2000 to 2021 with at least one author from Baranya County. Then we identified the further RAs that are assigned to these publications. These 29 biotechnology-related RAs (see Appendix 3) serve as possible scientific knowledge elements of the agents. Then we searched for the publications of all organizations (firms and university institutes as well) that represent an agent and identified their

² We consider the most popular IPC Subclasses that are assigned to at least 10% of the publications in each keyword search.

³ It gives the same result as if we searched for Research Area = Biotechnology and Applied Microbiology.

publications with biotechnology-related research areas. To determine the expertise level, we used full counting of the publications and normalized them. For normalization, the number of publications is simply divided by the age⁴ of the organization, so the expertise level expresses the number of publications of the agent per year in the given RA. The knowledge space determines the proximity relationships between the different knowledge elements. It forms the basis for knowledge acquisition, as during the research process agents more easily achieve new knowledge elements if they are closer in the knowledge space.

There are two distinct knowledge spaces: a technological and a scientific knowledge space. Although there is a tendency that university institutes have mainly scientific knowledge while firms possess more technological knowledge, all agents possibly have both types of knowledge elements. The technological knowledge space builds up from the proximity network of technological knowledge fields, operationalized by IPC subclasses of the selected patent dataset, while the scientific knowledge space builds up from the proximity network of scientific knowledge fields, operationalized by the WoS RAs of the selected scientific publications. We use the Jaccard index to measure the proximity of the technological knowledge fields TF_k and TF_l ($k, l = 1, 2, \dots, L$) where L denotes the total number of technological knowledge fields as normalized co-occurrences:

$$J_{kl} = \frac{c_{kl}}{c_k + c_l - c_{kl}}$$

Where c_{kl} denotes the number of co-occurrences of the technological knowledge fields TF_k and TF_l in a patent while c_k and c_l denote the number of occurrences of knowledge field TF_k and TF_l in the given set of patents. The same formula is used to define the proximity of scientific knowledge fields SF_m and SF_n ($m, n = 1, 2, \dots, N$), where N denotes the total number of scientific fields:

$$J_{mn} = \frac{c_{mn}}{c_m + c_n - c_{mn}}$$

The two distinct knowledge spaces need to be connected to make the learning process possible between the scientific and the technological sphere. In the real world, it means that during the research process, from a technology field as a starting point, a scientific area as a research target can be reached and vice versa. In the model, we use an ontology of industrial biotechnology developed in the KNOWMAK project (Maynard et al. 2020) to link scientific and technological knowledge elements of the agents. The KNOWMAK ontology contains 23 subfields of industrial biotechnology which we use to build a concordance table between the two types of knowledge, we define first the relationship between the KNOWMAK Subfields and the technological and the scientific knowledge fields separately. It results two matrices: S is an N -by- K matrix, where rows are the scientific knowledge fields (represented by WoS RAs) and columns are the KNOWMAK Subfields, and T is a K -by- L matrix, where rows are the KNOWMAK Subfields and columns are the technological knowledge fields (represented by IPC Subclasses). S builds upon the occurrences of RAs on the publications during a search for the

⁴ The age of the organization is calculated as: 2021 minus the year of the first publication of the organization in the WoS collection.

KNOWMAK Subfields as keywords at WoS. Similarly, T is defined on the basis of the occurrences of IPC codes on the patents during a search for the KNOWMAK Subfields as keywords at patents.google.com.

For the scientific side of the concordance table, we count the co-occurrences of KNOWMAK Subfields as keywords and WoS RAs on the publications and normalize this number with the sum of the publications assigned with the given keyword plus the sum of the publications in the given RA among the current set of publications. The elements of the S matrix are calculated as:

$$s_{nk} = \frac{a_{nk}}{a_n + a_k}$$

where $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$, N is being the total number of scientific fields (WoS RAs), $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$, where K denotes the total number of KNOWMAK Subfields. a_{nk} is the co-occurrence of the scientific field n and the KNOWMAK Subfield k , a_n is the number of occurrences of scientific field n , while a_k is the number of occurrences of KNOWMAK Subfield k . The relevant selection of WoS Research Areas is given in Appendix 3.

The matrix for the technological side of the concordance table is similarly based on the co-occurrences of KNOWMAK Subfields as keywords and IPC codes on the patents. This number is normalized by the sum of the patents assigned with the given keyword plus the sum of the patents in the given IPC Subclass (3-digit) among the current set of publications.

$$t_{kl} = \frac{a_{kl}}{a_k + a_l}$$

$l = 1, 2, \dots, L$, where L denotes the total number of technological knowledge fields. a_{kl} is the co-occurrence of the KNOWMAK Subfield k and the IPC code l , a_k is the number of occurrences of KNOWMAK Subfield k , a_l is the number of occurrences of IPC Subfield l . The concrete list of IPC Subclasses for this study is given Appendix 1.

The final concordance table arises from the multiplication of these two matrices:

$$C = ST,$$

where C is an N-by-L matrix, whose rows are scientific, and columns are technological knowledge fields. Thus, by construction, a single element of C indicates the empirically based probability that a model agent successfully acquires new knowledge in its research, i.e., that it reaches a specific scientific knowledge field when it starts from the given technological field and vice versa.

5 Implementation and simulation

The model is currently being implemented in the NetLogo simulation platform, which is a multi-agent fully programable modeling environment. This platform is widely used for agent-based modeling in social sciences, since it is well suited for modeling complex systems developing over time.

5.1 Calibration

Agent characteristics, such as knowledge endowment and the organizational figures are initialized based on the abovementioned empirical data. System parameters that do not have an empirical counterpart will be calibrated as can be seen in Table 1.

Name	Possible values	Initialization
Organization type	{firm, university institute}	empirical
Number of employees	\mathbb{N}_+	empirical
Age	\mathbb{NN}_+	empirical
Knowledge endowment		
- Knowledge fields	$\mathbb{N} \in \{1, \dots, X\}$, where $X = SF + TF$	empirical
- Expertise level	\mathbb{R}_+	empirical
Learning strategy	{strengthening, catching up, related variety, unrelated variety}	calibrated
Collaboration strategy	{internal, collaborative}	calibrated
Way of learning	{active, passive}	calibrated

Table 1: Overview of the empirical and the calibrated input variables

The data cover a 20-year period. We split up this to two 10 years long periods, in order to use the first period for initialization and the second period for calibration. According to the data from the first 10 years, the initial values of variables are defined. The calibration process starts from this state Through the calibration process, we will set the model parameters in a way that provides the best fit to the observed output data, namely patents and publications.

Name	Symbol	Range
Length of collaboration memory	lcm	\mathbb{N}_+
Share of agents with learning potential	α	[0, 1]
Share of agents with active learning strategy	β	[0, 1]
Share of agents with collaborative strategy	γ	[0, 1]
Share of agents with region external partner outreach	δ	[0, 1]
Share of technological knowledge gain that becomes a patent	ε	[0, 1]
Share of scientific knowledge gain that becomes a publication	ϕ	[0, 1]
Share of agents with specialization strategy	η	[0, 1]
Share of specializing agents with strengthening sub-strategy	κ	[0, 1]
Share of diversifying agents with related variety sub-strategy	λ	[0, 1]

Table 2: Overview of the model parameters

The baseline scenario represents the case where model parameters are calibrated towards total patent and publication output of the region. The aim of the empirical calibration is to fit the model parameters in such a way that the resulting output variables lie within a range of the selected empirical parameters. We follow Thiele et al. (2014) and Neuländtner (2020) applying a cost-function approach that punishes parameter combinations that lead to outputs that lie outside empirically justified range of values. This

calibration procedure defines the model parameters in such a way that least-cost and at the same time plausible parameter combinations are chosen to obtain an empirically justified baseline scenario.

5.2 Scenario exploration

The simulation results describe the knowledge created in the region, represented by the number of publications and patents, both aggregated at the region level and at the level of research areas and technological fields. Thus, pathways for regional specialization are being explored. Hereby, future-oriented simulations of the baseline scenario represent the business-as-usual, i.e., the innovation performance of the region (implicitly) including the actual policy framework in place. To compare the business-as-usual scenario with potential policy alternatives, the model parameters are changed to represent alternative options that are in discussion. Two important scenarios will be considered.

- Scenario A: Increased support for scientific and technological collaboration at the region level and beyond. In this scenario, knowledge exchange among the agents is favored according to the existing technological and (evolving) collaboration structures.
- Scenario B: Alternative agent strategies with respect to their tendency for technological specialization or diversification. This scenario explores the effectiveness of region-level smart specialization strategies.

6 Summary and concluding remarks

The paper describes the conceptualization and implementation of an agent-based model of knowledge creation in a regional biotech innovation system embedded in a less-favored region. It is empirically based on data from the Pécs city region in Southern Hungary. Compared to previous models of knowledge creation in the biotech sector, it focuses on the early stage of innovation pathway development including not only the industry agents but also university sector agents at the level of institutes. To underpin the model at the agent- and system-level with empirical data, personal interviews were conducted and patent data as well as publication data are employed through an elaborated initialization and calibration procedure. Currently, the model is being implemented and calibrated for baseline scenario definition. Further progress is to be expected in the upcoming months.

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8 References

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Appendix 1: IPC subclasses used

IPC-3	Description
A01K	ANIMAL HUSBANDRY; AVICULTURE; APICULTURE; PISCICULTURE; FISHING; REARING OR BREEDING ANIMALS, NOT OTHERWISE PROVIDED FOR; NEW BREEDS OF ANIMALS
A61C	DENTISTRY; APPARATUS OR METHODS FOR ORAL OR DENTAL HYGIENE
A61F	FILTERS IMPLANTABLE INTO BLOOD VESSELS; PROSTHESES; DEVICES PROVIDING PATENCY TO, OR PREVENTING COLLAPSING OF, TUBULAR STRUCTURES OF THE BODY, e.g. STENTS; ORTHOPAEDIC, NURSING OR CONTRACEPTIVE DEVICES; FOMENTATION; TREATMENT OR PROTECTION OF EYES OR EARS; BANDAGES, DRESSINGS OR ABSORBENT PADS; FIRST-AID KITS
A61K	PREPARATIONS FOR MEDICAL, DENTAL, OR TOILET PURPOSES
A61L	METHODS OR APPARATUS FOR STERILISING MATERIALS OR OBJECTS IN GENERAL; DISINFECTION, STERILISATION, OR DEODORISATION OF AIR; CHEMICAL ASPECTS OF BANDAGES, DRESSINGS, ABSORBENT PADS, OR SURGICAL ARTICLES; MATERIALS FOR BANDAGES, DRESSINGS, ABSORBENT PADS, OR SURGICAL ARTICLES
A61M	DEVICES FOR INTRODUCING MEDIA INTO, OR ONTO, THE BODY; DEVICES FOR TRANSDUCING BODY MEDIA OR FOR TAKING MEDIA FROM THE BODY; DEVICES FOR PRODUCING OR ENDING SLEEP OR STUPOR [5]
A61P	SPECIFIC THERAPEUTIC ACTIVITY OF CHEMICAL COMPOUNDS OR MEDICINAL PREPARATIONS
B01L	CHEMICAL OR PHYSICAL LABORATORY APPARATUS FOR GENERAL USE
B82Y	SPECIFIC USES OR APPLICATIONS OF NANOSTRUCTURES; MEASUREMENT OR ANALYSIS OF NANOSTRUCTURES; MANUFACTURE OR TREATMENT OF NANOSTRUCTURES
C02F	TREATMENT OF WATER, WASTE WATER, SEWAGE, OR SLUDGE
C07K	PEPTIDES
C08G	MACROMOLECULAR COMPOUNDS OBTAINED OTHERWISE THAN BY REACTIONS ONLY INVOLVING CARBON-TO-CARBON UNSATURATED BONDS
C08J	WORKING-UP; GENERAL PROCESSES OF COMPOUNDING; AFTER-TREATMENT NOT COVERED BY SUBCLASSES C08B, C08C, C08F, C08G or C08H
C09D	COATING COMPOSITIONS, e.g. PAINTS, VARNISHES OR LACQUERS; FILLING PASTES; CHEMICAL PAINT OR INK REMOVERS; INKS; CORRECTING FLUIDS; WOODSTAINS; PASTES OR SOLIDS FOR COLOURING OR PRINTING; USE OF MATERIALS THEREFOR
C12M	APPARATUS FOR ENZYMOLOGY OR MICROBIOLOGY
C12N	MICROORGANISMS OR ENZYMES; COMPOSITIONS THEREOF; PROPAGATING, PRESERVING, OR MAINTAINING MICROORGANISMS; MUTATION OR GENETIC ENGINEERING; CULTURE MEDIA
C12P	MICROORGANISMS OR ENZYMES; COMPOSITIONS THEREOF; PROPAGATING, PRESERVING, OR MAINTAINING MICROORGANISMS; MUTATION OR GENETIC ENGINEERING; CULTURE MEDIA
C12Q	MEASURING OR TESTING PROCESSES INVOLVING ENZYMES, NUCLEIC ACIDS OR MICROORGANISMS; COMPOSITIONS OR TEST PAPERS THEREFOR; PROCESSES OF PREPARING SUCH COMPOSITIONS; CONDITION-RESPONSIVE CONTROL IN MICROBIOLOGICAL OR ENZYMOLOGICAL PROCESSES
C12Y	ENZYMES
G01N	INVESTIGATING OR ANALYSING MATERIALS BY DETERMINING THEIR CHEMICAL OR PHYSICAL PROPERTIES
G16B	BIOINFORMATICS, i.e. INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY [ICT] SPECIALLY ADAPTED FOR GENETIC OR PROTEIN-RELATED DATA PROCESSING IN COMPUTATIONAL MOLECULAR BIOLOGY
Y02E	REDUCTION OF GREENHOUSE GAS [GHG] EMISSIONS, RELATED TO ENERGY GENERATION, TRANSMISSION OR DISTRIBUTION
Y02W	CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION TECHNOLOGIES RELATED TO WASTEWATER TREATMENT OR WASTE MANAGEMENT
A01H	NEW PLANTS OR PROCESSES FOR OBTAINING THEM; PLANT REPRODUCTION BY TISSUE CULTURE TECHNIQUES
C07G	COMPOUNDS OF UNKNOWN CONSTITUTION

Appendix 2: Attribution of patents to organizations

Special case of inventor affiliation	Model implementation
Applicant is the University of Pecs and the inventors are also from the University	We identify their department and we assign the given share of the knowledge unit to the department
Inventors with more than one affiliation	We split up the knowledge unit between the affiliations so the sum will remain constant
Applicant is a firm from the region and inventors have university affiliation	We treat them as double affiliations, employees of the firm and university members. We split up the knowledge unit between the affiliations so the sum will remain constant.
Inventor address is in the region, but the patent is applied by an organization from another region while we do not have any other information about the inventor	We treat them as double affiliations: employees of the extra-regional organization and a regional self-employed entrepreneur. We split up the knowledge unit between the affiliations so only the regional part adds to the regional agent's knowledge and the sum will remain constant.
Inventor has died or retired	If we know the last employer of the person, we assign the knowledge unit to this organization.

Appendix 3: Biotechnology-related Research Areas

Research Areas
Biotechnology Applied Microbiology
Biochemistry Molecular Biology
Research Experimental Medicine
Microbiology
Genetics Heredity
Virology
Science Technology Other Topics
Mycology
Agriculture
Immunology
Medical Ethics
Pharmacology Pharmacy
Polymer Science
Biophysics
Cell Biology
Chemistry
Electrochemistry
Plant Sciences
Engineering
Entomology
Pathology
Toxicology
Computer Science
Energy Fuels
Environmental Sciences Ecology
Food Science Technology
Mathematical Computational Biology
Mathematics
Oncology

Appendix 4: KET industrial biotechnology subclasses

KET industrial biotechnology subclasses
Animal biotechnology
Applied immunology
Assay systems
Biologics
Biomaterials
Biomimetics
Cell delivery
DNA sequencing
Environmental biotechnology
Expression systems
Gene delivery
Genomics
Industrial microbiology
Metabolomics
Molecular engineering
Nanobiotechnology
Nucleic acid therapeutics
Oligo delivery
Protein and peptide delivery
Proteomics
Regenerative medicine
Stem-cell biotechnology
Tissue engineering